
AN ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL EFFICIENCY OF PACS IN SATARA DISTRICT: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT:

India's economy is based mostly on the growth of the agricultural and its allied sector that contributes about 21% of the country's (GVA). Over the period, the need for agricultural credit has been increased and that has given rise to organized and unorganized sector of lending. The current paper reviews the performance of PACS in the study area. The main objective focuses on the growth and development of primary agricultural credit cooperatives societies in Satara district of state Maharashtra. For the study, the statistical techniques like mean, coefficient of variance were used with the use of secondary sources of data to analyze the performance of the primary agricultural credit societies in the study area. The study finds that the growth of profitability is inconsistent or unstable during the study period and there is no satisfactory growth of PACS in Satara district.

Keywords: Primary agricultural credit cooperative societies (PACS), growth, development, Agricultural inputs, Credit, CAGR, NABSCOB

I. INTRODUCTION

PACS are the banks which are situated in rural area and play a very important role in rural credit system by performing their activities on co-operative principles and also these banks are worked under the District Credit Co-operative Banks. They provide short term and medium term loan to rural people to meet their financial requirements. But, the rural people still depend on unorganized sources such as money lenders in village, mandies, traders etc. So, various measures taken by Government to reduce these unorganized sources through the establishment of PACS in rural areas. In order know the role of PACS in agricultural development in India the study has been undertaken.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the growth and development of the PACS in study area.
2. To study the performance of the PACS in the Satara District.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data collection is the most important step in the process of research work. The methodology of data collection for present research work is planned in such a manner that every bit of information pertains to different aspects of performance has been collected. The researcher has been used primary data and secondary data for the research purpose. The secondary data necessary for the present research work especially for the theoretical analysis has been gathered by the review of past literature and the statistical information is collected by personal visit to: DCC Satara, Wai, Javali, Koregoan and various talukas, Annual Report, Cooperative Societies, Published Unpublished Report, Nabsco Report, Various Reports of PACS, Journal, Article and News of Cooperative Sectors and Various Audit Report of Management

IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Thirupathi, T. (2013), in the paper entitled "An analysis of financial performance of select primary agricultural cooperative credit societies in Mettur Taluk, Salem District". The goal of this research was to look at the profitability, liquidity, and solvency of the selected PACS. 2. To make a financial comparison. 3. Make recommendations to improve the financial performance of the PACS in question. The researcher used secondary sources to write the entire study. Finally, he found that the Navappaty PACS Gross Profit Ratio showed an upward tendency, and the debtor's turnover ratio grew.

Ramananda M. S, & Jayaprakash M. (2012), "Impact on Vyadyanathan Committee wangapally Primary Agricultural Cooperative Credit Society's Recommendations." The purpose of this article is to investigate the impact of the Vyadhanathan committee's recommendations concerning the Wangapally Primary Agricultural Cooperative Credit Society. The purpose of this study is to look into the financial aspects of the Wangapally Primary Agricultural Cooperative Credit Society. This research used secondary data. The recent adjustment to the Vaiydhyathan committee's recommendation that the government keep 25% of equity capital in the event of PACS should be seriously considered, according to the researcher. Attempts should be made to either completely remove government equity from the PACS or to recognize the PACS as quasi-government ventures with new performance standards.

V. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

Ho: There is no significant relationship between actual performance and organizational goals.

H1: There is no significant relationship between actual performance and organizational goals.

VI. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

A. Capital of PACS in India:

A Primary Agricultural Credit Society is organized at grass-root level of a village or a group of small villages. The details **Capital of PACS** in India are given in below table.

Table: 1: Table Showing Capital of PACS in India

Sr. No.	Year	Capital	AAGR
1	2008-09	700732	-----
2	2009-10	714842	0.020136086
3	2010-11	755117	0.056341122
4	2011-12	828010	0.096532061
5	2012-13	986830.9	0.191810365
6	2013-14	978880.4	-0.008056598
7	2014-15	1106828.6	0.130708716
8	2015-16	1228111	0.109576496
9	2016-17	1412155.4	0.149859744
10	2017-18	1414199.5	0.001447504
	Mean	1012570.68	0.08315061
	Max	1414199.5	0.191810365
	Min	700732	-0.008056598
	SD	271691.0388	
	CAGR	0.072743453	

Source: Annual Report

The above table shows that the capital of PACS in India from the years of 2008-09 to 2017-18 during this year the mean amount of total capital is Rs: 1012570.68 and its average annual growth rate are 0.08315061. The maximum capital amount is 1414199.5 and AAGR is 0.191810365. on the other hand the minimum capital amount is 700732 and its minimum AAGR is -0.008056 during the study period there were standard deviation amount is 271691.0388 as well as CAGR is 0.072. It is concluded that during the study period in the year of 2013-14 capital was decreased. After this year of there is continuously growth in the capital during the study periods. As per the data it is observed that very less growth of the capital during the study periods in India. Because lack of capital increased by the government for the PACS.

B. Profitability of PACS in Satara:

Profit equals a company's revenues minus expenses. Earning a profit is important to a small business because profitability impacts whether a company can secure financing from a bank, attract investors to fund its operations and grow its business. Companies cannot remain in business without turning a profit. Net income or net earnings is a measure of the profitability of a venture after accounting for all costs. The details of net profit of the selected PACS are given in below table.

Table: 2: Table showing profitability of PACS in Satara

Sr. No.	Year	Amount In Lakhs	AAGR
1	2009-10	89.59	
2	2010-11	119.45	0.333296
3	2011-12	122.95	0.029301
4	2012-13	111.16	-0.09589
5	2013-14	149.16	0.34185
6	2014-15	212.17	0.422432
7	2015-16	233.87	0.102276
8	2016-17	234.83	0.004105
9	2017-18	209.8	-0.10659
10	2018-19	223.91	0.067255

	Avg. Mean	1706.9	0.122004
	MAX	1706.9	0.422432
	MIN	111.16	-0.10659
	SD	57.42379	
	CAGR	0.095926	

Source: Annual Report

The above table presents that the Profitability of PACS in Satara District from the year 2009-10 to 2018-19. The Average mean of Profitability amount is 170.6 and Mean of AAGR is 0.12. The Maximum Profitability is 234.83 and maximum Average growth is 0.42 during the study periods. The minimum profitability is 111.6 and minimum growth is -0.10 659. The amount of profitability standard deviation is 57.42 and Compound annual growth rate is 0.09 during the study periods. It is understood that there is growth of profitability very fluctuating in the study periods. Here seen that there is no satisfactory growth of PACS in Satara district.

C. Actual Target and Distribution of PACS Satara District:

The below table explains year wise target and distribution of loan in Satara district during the study period.

Table: 3: Actual Performance and organizational goals.

Sr. No	Year	Target	Growth	Distribution	Growth
1	2010-11	46495	0	56463	0
2	2011-12	53435	0.14926	64855	0.148628
3	2012-13	64300	0.20333	100703	0.552741
4	2013-14	76400	0.18818	107067	0.063196
5	2014-15	10080	12.1937	125142	0.16882
6	2015-16	1145	-0.8863	129678	0.036247
7	2016-17	1350	0.17852	105012	-0.19021
8	2017-18	1350	0	120386	0.146402
9	2018-19	1350	0	173342	0.439885
10	2019-20	1400	0.03703	155817	-0.1011
11	2020-21	1300	-0.0714	186308	0.195685
	Min	46495	-0.88636	56463	-0.19021
	Max	1008004	12.193	186308	0.552741
	Average	237898.7	1.792287	120580.3	0.140217

Source: Annual Report

The above table presents that the Actual Performance and organizational goals of PACS in Satara District from the year 2009-10 to 2018-19. It is observed that there is target mean value is 237898.7 and its average growth was 1.792287. There is actual distribution value is 120580.3 and its growth value is 0.14. It means that actual performance is more than organizational goals but there is negative growth in the last five years. There is need of increase the crop loan amount for the agricultural developments.

Testing of Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant relationship between actual performance and organizational goals.

H1: There is significant relationship between actual performance and organizational goals.

For this hypothesis researcher has set two variables target of loan (organizational goals) and distribution of loan (actual performance). After researcher has use paired sample T test. The below table explain in details.

Table: 4

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Actual performance	.4603	11	4.43	1.335
	Organizational goals.	.1328	11	.2161	.0651

The above table indicates that paired sample statistics of actual performance and organizational goals. The actual performance mean value is .4603 and mean value of Organizational goals .1328.

Table: 5

Paired Samples Correlations				
		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Actual performance & organizational goals.	11	0.20	0.57

The above table shows the paired sample correlation of actual performance and organizational goals there is correlation between two values is .010 it means there is low correlations.

Table: 6

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Actual performance and organizational goals.	.32759	4.43346	1.33674	-2.65085	3.30603	.245	10	0.511

It found that P value (Sig Value) is greater than level of significance (0.05), It means that accepted null hypothesis: **Ho:** There is no significant relationship between actual performance and organizational goals in the Study area is rejected.

VII. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. It is understood that during the study periods there are ups and downs the AAGR after in the year 2014-15 there were AAGR is increased. It is Compound annual growth rate is very low.
2. It is understood that there is growth of profitability very fluctuating in the study periods. Here seen that there is no satisfactory growth of PACS in Satara district.
3. It found that actual performance is more than organizational goals but there is negative growth in the last five years. There is need of increase the crop loan amount for the agricultural developments.

VIII. SUGGESTION

1. **Analyze the Causes of Negative Growth:** Before increasing the crop loan amount, it's important to understand why there has been negative growth in the past five years. Conduct a thorough analysis of the factors contributing to this decline. This may involve assessing market conditions, weather patterns, agricultural practices, or policy changes.
2. **Increase Loan Amounts:** If the analysis suggests that increasing the crop loan amount is necessary, do so cautiously. Ensure that the increased loan amounts are reasonable and sustainable for farmers. Striking the right balance is crucial to avoid overburdening farmers with debt.
3. **Promote Diversification:** Encourage farmers to diversify their crops and explore alternative income sources. This can help mitigate risks associated with negative growth in specific crops and promote overall agricultural development.

IX. CONCLUSIONS

It concluded that over the study period, there have been fluctuations in the Average Annual Growth Rate (AAGR). In particular, there was an increase in AAGR after the year 2014-15, but overall, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) remains low. This may indicate inconsistent or slow growth in some area or industry. Profitability growth has been inconsistent or unstable during the study period. Additionally, it mentions that there is unsatisfactory growth of Primary Agricultural Credit Cooperative Societies (PACS) in Satara district, which may be a concern for agricultural development in that region. It concluded that despite surpassing organizational goals, there has been negative growth in the last five years. To address this issue and support agricultural development, it is recommended to increase the amount of crop loans provided.

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